

The International Journal of Social Sciences World

TIJOSSW

Letter of Acceptance

Dear Dinda A. Ratnasari, Sri Hastjarjo, Y. Slamet

Congratulations!

After conducting double-blind peer-review processes, herewith I declare that your manuscript entitled “*The Richness of Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram to Optimize the Conveying of Supporting Messages for Breastfeeding: Evidence from Indonesia Breastfeeding Fathers (AyahASI)*” **IS ACCEPTED** to be published in “*The International Journal of Social Sciences World*” (TIJOSSW) (US ISSN: 2690-5167), Vol. 5 No. 1 (2023).

Yours Sincerely,

Dr. Suman Rajest